

Quantum Mechanics and Hydrodynamics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. July 22, 2020

In a previous note (1), we investigated a process (as described in (2)) for converting a hydrodynamical equation, following from Boltzmann's transport equation, into the Schrodinger equation. We argued that two distribution functions $f(p,x,t)$ were used. In this note, we try to argue that a distribution function (related to conditional probability $P(p/x)$) satisfies the classical hydrodynamical equation for a conserved momentum (with density replaced by square root of density i.e. the wavefunction). In other words, one cannot use $\int dp f(p,x,t) = \text{spatial density}(x,t)$, but must rather use $\int dp f(p,x,t) = W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \text{square root of spatial density}$. $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ contains complex probability terms $\exp(ipx)$ which also have an effect on the result. For the quantum case, $f(p,x,t) = a(p) \exp(ipx)$, we argue. Thus, there seems to be a link between quantum mechanics and hydrodynamics, although only through conditional probability and $W(x,t)$. We consider bound state quantum mechanics in this note.

Conditional Probability and Spatial Density in Bound State Quantum Mechanics

Bound state quantum mechanics seems to be based on conditional probability $P(p/x)$ i.e. there is a momentum distribution at x (with each momentum occurring at a different time as there is only one particle). The potential $V(x)$ is considered to be stochastic, having the form $V(x)$ on average. Thus, if a particle has momentum p_1 at x at t , there are various probabilities for it to receive p_i within Δx , due to the potential. If one uses:

$$P(p/x) = a(p)g(p,x)/W(x) \quad \text{where } W(x)=\text{wavefunction and } g(p,x) = \exp(ipx) \quad ((1))$$

one may consider average energy conservation at each point x :

$$\text{Sum over } p \quad p^2/2m a(p)f(p,x)/W(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((2))$$

For $g(p,x)=\exp(ipx)$, ((2)) is equivalent to the Schrodinger equation because minus the second derivative with respect to x yields p^2 . If one considers the bound state Schrodinger equation and writes $W(x)$ and $V(x)$ as Fourier series and collects terms related to $g(x,p)=\exp(ipx)$ (orthonormal basis) one finds:

$$a(p) p^2/2m + \text{Sum over } k \quad V(k)a(p-k) = E a(p) \quad ((3)) \quad \text{where } V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \quad V(k)\exp(ikx)$$

Thus at x , one may consider an $\exp(ipx)$ or alternatively various $\exp(i(p-k)x)$ which combine with V_k to make $\exp(ipx)$. Thus, there is dynamics and cycling continually occurring. It is possible to write $P(p/x)$ for a specific p and calculate averages, but it seems that due to the action of the

potential, one also has an $\exp(ikx)$ at x which then is knocked into $\exp(ipx)$. If one considers small regions where only one hit occurs, it seems that the physical situation is described by:

$$\text{Sum over } p_1, p_2 \ a(p_1) \exp(ip_1x) \ a(p_2) \exp(ip_2x) \quad ((4))$$

which includes cycling of p waves that is occurring. Thus, ((4)) is taken to be the spatial density, although conservation of energy follows from $P(p/x)$ which does not use this cycling. This seems to cause quantum mechanics to differ from classical statistical mechanics.

For a quantum bound state, there exists an average p and an average $p^*p/2m$ using $P(p/x)$. This raises the question: Is there a link with hydrodynamics (Boltzmann's transport equation) and $P(p/x)$? Is there an $f(p,x,t)$ such that $\text{Integral } dp \ f(p,x,t) = W(x,t)$ and not spatial density as in usual hydrodynamics? (Here we use one dimension, but later show results hold for three dimensions.)

Hydrodynamics

In (2) and (3), regular hydrodynamics follows from the Boltzmann transport equation with:

$$\text{Integral } d^n p \ f(p,x,t) = \text{density}(x,t) \quad ((5))$$

We suggest that for bound state quantum mechanics, ((5)) be replaced with:

$$\text{Integral } d^n p_1 \ d^n p_2 \ f(p_1,x,t)f(p_2,x,t) = \text{density}(x,t) \quad ((6))$$

$$\text{Or } \text{Integral } d^n p \ f(p,x,t) = W(x) \quad ((7))$$

We argued above that density in bound state quantum mechanics is due to combinations of $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x)a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x)$ where $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ is associated with $P(p/k)$. Thus, we argue that a quantum transport equation should be based on an $f(p,x,t)$ associated with $P(p/k)$ and following ((7)). The objective then becomes to determine whether ((7)) with $f(p,x,t)=f(p,x)=a(p)\exp(ipx)$ is consistent with the ideas of the Boltzmann transport equation.

We begin with ((7)) with $f(p,x)= a(p) \exp(ipx)$ for bound state quantum mechanics and define an average as:

$$\langle X \rangle_p = \langle X \rangle = [\text{Integral } dp \ f(p,x) X] / W(x) \quad ((8))$$

From Boltzmann transport theory, the following conservation equation may be applied to quantum conditional probability averages (3): (d/dt is the partial derivative and we use 1-D for simplicity)

$$d/dt (W X) + d/dx \langle W p/m X \rangle_p - W \langle p/m dX/dx \rangle_p - W/m \langle F dX/d(p/m) \rangle = 0 \quad ((9))$$

We assume $dF/dp = 0$ where $F = \text{force} = -dV/dx$. For $X = p/m$ one has in 1-D (3):

$$\{d/dt (\text{partial}) + u d/dx\} u = 1/m F - 1/W d/dx \{W <(v-u)(v-u)>\} \quad ((10))$$

where $u = \langle v \rangle$. For the quantum bound state problem:

$$\langle p^* p \rangle = -d/dx d/dx W / W \quad \text{and} \quad \langle p \rangle = -i d/dx W / W \quad ((11))$$

Thus, minus signs and $i = \sqrt{-1}$ are important in the quantum case.

For one dimension $\langle (v-u)(v-u) \rangle = \langle v^* v \rangle - \langle v \rangle \langle v \rangle$

From the LHS of ((10)) with $m=1$: $u du/dx = -dW/dx (1/W) \{ d/dx d/dx W / W - (dW/dx/W)^2 \}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{From the RHS of ((10)): } & - (1/W) d/dx \{ W [-d/dx d/dx W / W + (dW/dx / W)^2] \} \\ & = \{ (d/dx)^3 W \} / W + (dW/dx / W)^3 - 2 dW/dx d/dx d/dx W (1/(W^*W)) \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the hydrodynamic equation for the conditional probability $f(p,x) = a(p) \exp(ipx)$ appears to be satisfied for one dimension.

This equation is identical to taking d/dx of the bound state Schrodinger equation written in the form of ((2)).

For three dimensions, one has:

No sum on double j 's below and $d_j = d/dx_j$

$$\text{LHS} - d_j W/W \{ d_j d_i W / W - d_i W d_j W / (W^*W) \}$$

$$\text{RHS} - 1/W \{ -d_i d_j d_j W / W + d_j d_i W d_j W / W + d_i W d_j d_j W / W - d_i W / (W^*W) (d_j W)(d_j W) \}$$

On the RHS, the first and third terms cancel and one again obtains the spatial derivative of the Schrodinger equation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue one may apply the conserved momentum classical Boltzmann transport equation to conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ from quantum mechanics and obtain the derivative of the Schrodinger equation. Thus, the conditional probability $P(p/x)$ or rather $a(p) \exp(ipx)$ seems to satisfy hydrodynamics with the change that: $\text{Integral } f(p,x) dp = W(x)$ where $f(p,x) = a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. In usual hydrodynamics, the spatial density appears in place of $W(x)$ which must be used in the quantum case. We argue that the classical result: $\text{Integral } dp f(p,x,t) = \text{density}(x,t)$ is replaced with:

$\int dp_1 f(p_1, x, t) \int dp_2 f(p_2, x, t) = W(x)W(x)$. In quantum mechanics, we argue that spatial density arises because one has $\exp(ipx)$ terms and $\exp(ikx)$ which interact with the potential to form $\exp(ipx)$, thus in a region Δx one is dealing with all combinations $\exp(ip_1x) a(p_1) a(p_2) \exp(ip_2x)$ leading to a spatial density of the form $W(x)W(x)$, even though the dynamics (and hydrodynamics) apply to $a(p) \exp(ipx)$.

For average quantities, one may use: $\langle X \rangle_p = [\int dp X a(p) \exp(ipx)] / W(x)$. $-i d/dx \exp(ipx)$ yields $p \exp(ipx)$ so one must be careful with signs when evaluating $\langle p \rangle$ and $\langle p^*p \rangle$. Nevertheless, it seems that conditional probability from quantum mechanics (which satisfies conservation of energy at each x point for a bound state) also satisfies the momentum conservation Boltzmann transport equation from hydrodynamics in one and three dimensions. It is just connected to spatial density in an unusual manner (when compared with classical statistical mechanics.)

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Conditional Probability $P(p/x)$ versus Hydrodynamic Approach to the Bound Schrodinger Equation (preprint, zenodo, 2020)
2. Kaniadakis, G. Statistical Origin of Quantum Mechanics (2018)
<https://arxiv.org/abs/quant-ph/0112049>
3. Huang, K. Statistical Mechanics (Wiley, 1983)